

Three Dimensional Trigonometry

1. BACKGROUND

Many branches of trigonometry have been investigated. Conventional Euclidean trigonometry defined with the unit circle and right triangles is well known. Spherical trigonometry involving the angles and sides of triangles on the surface of a sphere is also understood. Trigonometry for the angles and sides of tetrahedrons has been developed. Little research has been done on extending unit circle based trigonometry into 3-space and higher. The purpose of this paper is to explore the properties of the angles and functions of three dimensional trigonometry founded on the unit sphere.

2. INTRODUCTION

Our goal when we started this research was to discover a 3D trigonometry that extended the attributes of 2D trigonometry. The 3D angles should be solid and sum to $\pi/2$. The 3D functions should be periodic, symmetric, continuous, and the sum of their squares equal to one. At first our investigation was based on tetrahedrons with an orthogonal angle. This led to problems with both the angles and the functions. The angles of tetrahedrons do not always sum to the same number like the angles of triangles. Although functions based on the squares of the areas of three sides of an orthogonal tetrahedron can sum to one, only half the values are obtained with real axes. Imaginary axes are required for the rest. We tried many different approaches to define the angles and functions with little success. Finally, after we abandoned the tetrahedrons, we found a trigonometric paradigm that satisfied most of our requirements based solely on the unit sphere with center at the origin.

In this paper we define, derive, and investigate the properties of the angles and functions of the paradigm. Sections 3 through 7 first show how the standard 2D trigonometry fits into the new model then extends these concepts by adding a third dimension with the same attributes as the second. Section 3 defines the angles and functions. The properties of the angles are discussed in Section 4. The function derivations are in Section 5. Section 6 defines the functions for angles less than $-\pi$ or greater than π . Section 7 investigates the periods, symmetry, and continuity of the functions. In the last Section we briefly discuss ND trigonometry. The degenerate forms of the 3D functions are examined in Appendix A.

Before we start investigating 3D trigonometry we must explain the notation that is used throughout this paper. The function names are formatted name-dimension for cosine functions and name-dimension-number for sine functions. Using this format, the base 3D functions are cosine3D, sine3D₁ and sine3D₂ and are abbreviated cos3D, sin3D₁ and sin3D₂.

3. ANGLE AND FUNCTION DEFINITIONS

The angles and functions for 2D trigonometry are redefined to fit this paradigm, then those concepts are extended to 3D. To explore these new concepts, we first need to introduce sign variables that are denoted with hats over the associated variables.

Definition 3.1 (Sign Variable).

$$\text{Let } v \text{ be a variable } \in \mathfrak{R}, \text{ then } \hat{v} = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } v < 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This lemma allows us to convert absolute values to sign variables and back again.

Lemma 3.2. *Absolute Value to Sign Variable* If $v \in \mathfrak{R}$, then $|v| = v\hat{v}$.

Proof. Absolute Value to Sign Variable The proof for this is directly from the definition of absolute value and 3.1. \square

3.1. 2D Trigonometry.

Although the resulting angles and functions are equivalent to those in the standard 2D trigonometry, we redefine them to comply with the the new paradigm. The new 2D angles and functions are based the unit circle as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. 2D Angles and Functions

3.1.1. Circular 2D Angles.

The 2D angles are defined using the unit circle centered at the origin and some point P on the unit circle. We show later that they are like the none orthogonal angles of a right triangle.

Definition 3.3 (2D Angle Definitions). Let

S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 ,
 point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S,
 point A have coordinates $(1, 0)$, and
 point B have coordinates $(0, \hat{y})$,

then

α_{2D} is the angle with vertex at the origin and rays through points P and B,
 has the same sign as x, and is $\in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$.
 β_{2D} is the angle with vertex at the origin and rays through points A and P,
 has the same sign as y, and is $\in [-\pi, \pi]$.

From this definition we can see that β_{2D} is defined like θ .

Theorem 3.4 (β_{2D} is θ). β_{2D} is equivalent to the traditional trigonometric angle θ .

Proof. The proof follows directly from the definition of β_{2D} as figure 1 shows. \square

Theorem 3.4 confirms that this paradigm is backwards compatible with the the traditional trigonometric angles.

Like the angles for conventional trigonometry, the 2D angles have directions. The arc for α_{2D} on S starts at B and goes to P. Its magnitude increases as P moves toward either A or $(-1, 0)$. The arc for β_{2D} starts at A and ends at P. Its magnitude increases as P moves toward $(-1, 0)$.

3.1.2. Circular 2D Functions.

In this paradigm, the circular 2D functions are defined using the unit circle centered at the origin and some point P on the unit circle. After we define the functions, we show that the sum of their squares is 1 and that they have the same values as the traditional trigonometric functions. See Figure 1.

Definition 3.5 (2D Function Definitions). Let

S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 ,
 point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S,
 L be the line through the origin and point P, and
 M be the line tangent to S at P,

then

$\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ is the x coordinate of point P.

$\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ is the y coordinate of point P.

$\tan 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ is the y coordinate of the intersection of line L and the line $x = 1$.

$\cot 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ is the x coordinate of the intersection of line L and the line $y = 1$.

$\sec 2D(\beta_{2D})$ is the x coordinate of the intersection of line M and the x axis.

$\csc 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ is the y coordinate of the intersection of line M and the y axis.

From this definition we see that the sum of the squares of $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ is one.

Theorem 3.6 (2D Sum of Squares). *The sum of the squares of $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ equals 1.*

2D Sum of Squares.

$$\cos^2 2D(\beta_{2D}) + \sin^2 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = 1.$$

$$x^2 + y^2 = 1 \quad \text{Definition 3.5.}$$

$$1 = 1 \quad \text{point P is on circle S.}$$

□

Since the functions are defined geometrically as the coordinates of points, we still need to prove that they are equivalent to the traditional trigonometric functions.

Theorem 3.7 (2D Function Values). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^2 and point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S, then*

$$\cos 2D(\beta_{2D}) = \cos(\theta) = x.$$

$$\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \sin(\theta) = y.$$

$$\tan 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \tan(\theta) = y/x.$$

$$\cot 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \cot(\theta) = x/y.$$

$$\sec 2D(\beta_{2D}) = \sec(\theta) = 1/x.$$

$$\csc 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \csc(\theta) = 1/y.$$

We need two lemmas to prove the function values. The first involves functions that equal the coordinate of a line. The second is for functions that are the coordinate of an N-space.

Lemma 3.8 (Function is a Coordinate of a Line). *Let*

the equation of a line of n dimensions be

$$\frac{x_1 - x_{01}}{x_1} = \frac{x_2 - x_{02}}{x_2} = \dots = \frac{x_n - x_{0n}}{x_n}$$

x_{0j} be the j^{th} coordinate on the line when $x_{0i} = 1$

then

$$x_{0j} = x_j/x_i.$$

Function is a Coordinate of a Line.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x_i - x0_i}{x_i} &= \frac{x_j - x0_j}{x_j} && \text{equation of the line.} \\ \frac{x_i - 1}{x_i} &= \frac{x_j - x0_j}{x_j} && \text{substitute 1 for the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ coordinate.} \\ x0_j &= \frac{x_j}{x_i} && \text{simplify.} \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.9 (Function is a Coordinate of an N-space). *Let*

*the equation of an N-space be $x0_1x_1 + x0_2x_2 + \dots + x0_nx_n = 1$.
 $(0, 0, \dots, x0_j, \dots, 0)$ be the intersection of the j^{th} axis and the N-space.*

then

$$x0_j = 1/x_j.$$

Function is a Coordinate of an N-space.

$$\begin{aligned} x0_ix_i + x0_jx_j + \dots + x0_nx_n &= 1. && \text{equation of the N-space.} \\ x0_jx_j &= 1 && \text{the other coordinates} = 0. \\ x0_j &= 1/x_j && \text{simplify.} \end{aligned}$$

□

2D Function Values. The proof that $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D}) = x$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = y$ are directly from Definition 3.5. For the other functions we know:

$$\begin{aligned} \tan 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) &= y/x && \text{Definition 3.5 and Lemma 3.8.} \\ \cot 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) &= x/y && \text{Definition 3.5 and Lemma 3.8.} \\ \sec 2D(\beta_{2D}) &= 1/x && \text{Definition 3.5 and Lemma 3.9.} \\ \csc 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) &= 1/y && \text{Definition 3.5 and Lemma 3.9.} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.7 shows that this paradigm is backwards compatible with the traditional trigonometric functions. Next we discuss the angles and functions of the new 3D trigonometry.

3.2. 3D Trigonometry.

We now define new 3D trigonometry angles and functions by extending the definitions of the 2D trigonometry into three dimensions. We convert circle S into a sphere and add a new point G on the z axis.

3.2.1. Spherical 3D Angles.

The 3D angles in this paradigm are defined using the unit sphere centered at the origin and some point P on the sphere. They have a relationship with $\pi/2$ that is similar to the 2D angles.

Definition 3.10 (3D Angle Definitions). Let

S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^3 ,
 point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S,
 point A have coordinates $(1, 0, 0)$,
 point B have coordinates $(0, \hat{y}, 0)$, and
 point G have coordinates $(0, 0, \hat{z})$,

then

α is the angle with vertex at the origin and rays through points P, B, and G,
 has the same sign as x, and is $\in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$.
 β is the angle with vertex at the origin and rays through points A, P, and G,
 has the same sign as y, and is $\in [-\pi, \pi]$.
 γ is the angle with vertex at the origin and rays through points A, B, and P,
 has the same sign as z, and is $\in [-\pi, \pi]$.

Definition 3.10 extends the definition of the flat 2D angles with arcs on the unit circle to solid 3D angles with triangles on the surface of the unit sphere. See figure 3.2.1.

The 3D angles also have directions. The triangle on the surface of S defined by α consists of the arcs that start at the arc from B to G and end at P. The magnitude of α increases as point P moves toward either point A or $(-1, 0, 0)$. The triangle created by β is composed of the arcs that start at A and go to the arc from P to G. The triangle on S defined by γ consists of the arcs that start at A and go to the arc from B to P. The magnitudes of β and γ increase as P moves toward $(-1, 0, 0)$.

3.2.2. Spherical 3D Functions.

The spherical 3D functions are defined using the unit sphere centered at the origin and some point P on the sphere. Their values are obtained by extending the concepts defined for the 2D functions into a third dimension. See Figure 3.2.2. There are two new types of functions that were not required in 2D, `sangent3D` abbreviated with `san3D(β, γ)` and `cosangent3D` abbreviated with `csn3D(β, γ)`.

Definition 3.11 (3D Function Definitions). Let

S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^3 ,
 point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S,
 L be the line through the origin and P, and
 M be the plane tangent to S at P,

FIGURE 2. 3D Angles

then

$\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ is the x coordinate of point P.

$\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is the y coordinate of point P.

$\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is the z coordinate of point P.

$\tan 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is the y coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $x = 1$.

$\cot 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is the x coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $y = 1$.

$\tan 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is the z coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $x = 1$.

$\cot 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is the x coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $z = 1$.

$\sec 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ is the x coordinate of the intersection of plane M and the x axis.

$\csc 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is the y coordinate of the intersection of plane M and the y axis.

$\csc 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is the z coordinate of the intersection of plane M and the z axis.

$\san 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ is the z coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $y = 1$.

$\csn 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ is the y coordinate of the intersection of line L and the plane $z = 1$.

FIGURE 3. 3D Functions

Using Definition 3.11 we show that the sum of the squares of $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$ is one.

Theorem 3.12 (3D Sum of Squares). *The sum of the squares of $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ equals 1.*

3D Sum of Squares.

$$\cos^2 3D(\beta, \gamma) + \sin^2 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) + \sin^2 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = 1.$$

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1 \quad \text{Definition 3.11.}$$

$$1 = 1 \quad \text{point P is on sphere S.}$$

□

We know that the 3D functions are defined as the coordinates of points. Now we determine their values.

Theorem 3.13 (3D Function Values). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 and point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , then*

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= x. & \tan 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= y/x. & \sec 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= 1/x. & \text{san} 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= z/y. \\ \sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= y. & \cot 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= x/y. & \csc 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= 1/y. & \text{csn} 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= y/z. \\ \sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= z. & \tan 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= z/x. & \csc 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= 1/z. \\ & & \cot 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= x/z. & & & & \end{aligned}$$

3D Function Values. The proof that $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) = x$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = y$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = z$ are directly from Definition 3.11 We prove the other functions like we did for the 2D functions using Lemmas 3.8 and 3.9.

$\tan 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = y/x$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.
$\cot 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = x/y$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.
$\tan 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = z/x$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.
$\cot 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = x/z$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.
$\sec 3D(\beta, \gamma) = 1/x$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.9.
$\csc 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = 1/y$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.9.
$\csc 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = 1/z$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.9.
$\text{san} 3D(\beta, \gamma) = z/y$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.
$\text{csn} 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = y/z$	Definition 3.11 and Lemma 3.8.

□

Theorem 3.13 explains how this paradigm extends the concepts of the 2D functions into a third dimension.

4. ANGLE PROPERTIES

In this section we examine the properties of the 2D angles including their relationship with $\pi/2$ and how to derive them given point P. Then we extend these concepts to the 3D angles. First we must define a new function mytangent that is defined at $\pm\pi/2$.

Since the derivation of the angles depends upon the tangent half angle function and angles in both 2D and 3D may be $\pm\pi$, we need a function that is equivalent to tangent except it is defined at $\pm\pi/2$. It allows the new trigonometric functions to accept inputs that are $\pm\pi$.

Definition 4.1 (mytangent).

$$\text{myt}(\theta) = \begin{cases} -\infty, & \text{if } \theta = -\pi/2 \\ \tan(\theta), & \text{if } \theta \in (-\pi/2, \pi/2) \\ \infty, & \text{if } \theta = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

4.1. 2D Angle Properties.

We first show how to derive the 2D angles given point P, then investigate their relationship with $\pi/2$, and finally examine the connection between the 2D angles and point P.

4.1.1. Deriving the 2D Angles.

Although we know how to easily obtain the value of the 2D angles using arc-sine and arc-cosine, we use a method that requires both the coordinates of point P. The reason for this becomes clear when we examine the 3D angles.

Proposition 4.2 (2D Half Angle Tangents). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 and point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S , then*

$$\text{myt}(\alpha_{2D}/2) = \frac{x}{1 + |y|}.$$

$$\text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2) = \frac{y}{1 + x}. \quad \beta_{2D} \text{ is undefined when point } P \text{ has coordinates } (-1, 0).$$

Proof. The proof of this is directly from the tangent half angle formula and Definition 4.1. For α_{2D} we take the absolute value of y to restrict it to within $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ as it is defined. \square

4.1.2. Sum of the 2D Angles.

Although it is not exactly like the angles of an orthogonal triangle, there is a relationship between the sum of α_{2D} and β_{2D} and $\pi/2$.

Theorem 4.3 (Sum of the 2D Angles). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 and point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S , then*

$$\alpha_{2D} + |\beta_{2D}| = \pi/2.$$

To prove this we start with Theorem 4.3 then divide by two and take the tangent of both sides. Next we apply the tangent sum formula and simplify. Then we switch the tangents to mytangents and apply Proposition 4.2. We finish by replacing the sum of the squares of x and y with one.

Sum of the 2D Angles.

$$\alpha_{2D} + |\beta_{2D}| = \pi/2.$$

$$\tan(\alpha_{2D}/2 + |\beta_{2D}|/2) = \tan(\pi/4) \quad \text{divide by 2, tangent of both sides.}$$

$$\frac{\tan(\alpha_{2D}/2) + \tan(|\beta_{2D}|/2)}{1 - \tan(\alpha_{2D}/2)\tan(|\beta_{2D}|/2)} = 1 \quad \text{tangent sum formula.}$$

$$\tan(\alpha_{2D}/2) + \tan(|\beta_{2D}|/2) = 1 - \tan(\alpha_{2D}/2)\tan(|\beta_{2D}|/2) \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$\text{myt}(\alpha_{2D}/2) + \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) = 1 - \text{myt}(\alpha_{2D}/2)\text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) \quad \text{Definition 4.1.}$$

$$\left(\frac{x}{1 + |y|}\right) + \left(\frac{|y|}{1 + x}\right) = 1 - \left(\frac{x}{1 + |y|}\right)\left(\frac{|y|}{1 + x}\right)$$

Definition 3.3 and Proposition 4.2.

$$x^2 + |y|^2 = 1 \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$1 = 1 \quad \text{point } P \text{ is on } S.$$

\square

4.1.3. Point P and the 2D Angles.

Both of the 2D angles have a special connection with one of the coordinates of point P. If the coordinate is $-1, 0,$ or $1,$ then the associated angle is $-\pi/2, 0,$ or $\pi/2,$ respectively, as shown in the table below.

4.2. 3D Angle Properties.

TABLE 1. Point P and the 2D Angles

Coordinate	x=-1	x=0	x=1	y=-1	y=0	y=1
2D Angle	$\alpha_{2D}=-\pi/2$	$\alpha_{2D}=0$	$\alpha_{2D}=\pi/2$	$\beta_{2D}=-\pi/2$	$\beta_{2D}=0$	$\beta_{2D}=\pi/2$

First we investigate how to derive the 3D angles given point P, next we show the relationship between the angles and $\pi/2$, then we examine the connection between the angles and the coordinates of point P.

4.2.1. Deriving the 3D Angles.

To determine the measurements of α , β , and γ , we must create a lemma to derive the magnitude for a solid angle involving two unit vectors that are on separate axes and another unit vector.

Lemma 4.4 (Measuring 3D Angles). *Let*

*S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 ,
point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S,
 \vec{u}_1 and \vec{u}_2 be different elements of $\{(1, 0, 0), (0, \hat{y}, 0), (0, 0, \hat{z})\}$, and
 ω be a solid angle defined by \vec{p} , \vec{u}_1 and \vec{u}_2 ,*

then

$$\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\omega}{2} \right) \right| = \frac{|\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{u}_1 \times \vec{u}_2)|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2}.$$

To prove this we start with the formula for a solid angle from Oosterom and Strackee [1]. We can drop all the magnitudes due to all the vectors having length one. Since \vec{u}_1 and \vec{u}_2 are on different axes, their dot product is zero. Then we evaluate the determinant of the matrix. Next we replace tangent with mytangent. We only want the magnitude, so we take the absolute value of the numerator. The minimum for the denominator is zero and occurs when P is $(-1, 0, 0)$, so it is never negative.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \tan \left(\frac{\omega}{2} \right) &= \frac{|\vec{p}\vec{u}_1\vec{u}_2|}{\|\vec{p}\|\|\vec{u}_1\|\|\vec{u}_2\| + (\vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1)\|\vec{u}_2\| + (\vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2)\|\vec{u}_1\| + (\vec{u}_1 \cdot \vec{u}_2)\|\vec{p}\|} \quad \text{by [1].} \\ &= \frac{|\vec{p}\vec{u}_1\vec{u}_2|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2 + \vec{u}_1 \cdot \vec{u}_2} \quad \text{the magnitudes of all the vectors is 1.} \\ &= \frac{|\vec{p}\vec{u}_1\vec{u}_2|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2} \quad \text{the dot product of } \vec{u}_1 \text{ and } \vec{u}_2 \text{ is zero.} \\ &= \frac{\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{u}_1 \times \vec{u}_2)}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2} \quad \text{evaluate the determinant.} \\ \text{myt} \left(\frac{\omega}{2} \right) &= \frac{\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{u}_1 \times \vec{u}_2)}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2} \quad \text{Definition 4.1.} \\ \left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\omega}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{u}_1 \times \vec{u}_2)|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{u}_2} \quad \text{take the absolute value for the magnitude.} \end{aligned}$$

□

Now we can apply this lemma to determine the values of α , β , and γ .

Proposition 4.5 (3D Half Angle Tangents). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^3 and P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , then*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{myt}\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) &= \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|}. \\ \text{myt}\left(\frac{\beta}{2}\right) &= \frac{y}{1 + x + |z|}. \\ \text{myt}\left(\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) &= \frac{z}{1 + x + |y|}. \end{aligned}$$

In the proof we first create vectors for the points A, B, G and P as defined in 3.10. Next we substitute each angle's vectors into Lemma 4.4. Then we evaluate the numerators and dot products. Next we drop the sign variables inside absolute values. Then we change to absolute value when a variable is multiplied by its sign. We set the sign of the angles with the sign variables for their associated coordinate. Finally we use the sign variables to remove the absolute values.

3D Half Angle Tangents. Let

S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^3 ,
point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S ,
 $\vec{p} = \overrightarrow{(x, y, z)}$, $\vec{v}_x = \overrightarrow{(1, 0, 0)}$, $\vec{v}_y = \overrightarrow{(0, \hat{y}, 0)}$ and $\vec{v}_z = \overrightarrow{(0, 0, \hat{z})}$,

then

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{v}_y \times \vec{v}_z)|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_y + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_z}, & \left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{v}_x \times \vec{v}_z)|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_x + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_z}, \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|\vec{p} \cdot (\vec{v}_x \times \vec{v}_y)|}{1 + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_x + \vec{p} \cdot \vec{v}_y} && \text{by Definition 3.10 and Lemma 4.4.} \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|x\hat{y}\hat{z}|}{1 + y\hat{y} + z\hat{z}}, & \left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|y\hat{z}|}{1 + x + z\hat{z}}, \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|\hat{y}\hat{z}|}{1 + x + y\hat{y}} && \text{evaluate the numerators and dot products.} \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|x|}{1 + y\hat{y} + z\hat{z}}, & \left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|y|}{1 + x + z\hat{z}}, \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|z|}{1 + x + y\hat{y}} && \text{drop sign variables in absolute values.} \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|x|}{1 + |y| + |z|}, & \left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|y|}{1 + x + |z|}, \\
\left| \text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) \right| &= \frac{|z|}{1 + x + |y|} && \text{Lemma 3.2.} \\
\text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) &= \frac{\hat{x}|x|}{1 + |y| + |z|}, & \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) &= \frac{\hat{y}|y|}{1 + x + |z|}, \\
\text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) &= \frac{\hat{z}|z|}{1 + x + |y|} && \text{definition 3.10.} \\
\text{myt} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) &= \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|}, & \text{myt} \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) &= \frac{y}{1 + x + |z|}, \\
\text{myt} \left(\frac{\gamma}{2} \right) &= \frac{z}{1 + x + |y|} && \text{Lemma 3.2.}
\end{aligned}$$

□

The results of the derivation of the 3D angles given point P is remarkably like that of the 2D angles.

4.2.2. Sum of the 3D Angles.

The relationship between the independent variables β and γ and the dependent variable α is similar to the relationship between β_{2D} and α_{2D} .

Theorem 4.6 (Sum of the 3D Angles).

$$\alpha + |\beta| + |\gamma| = \frac{\pi}{2}.$$

In the proof, we start with Theorem 4.6, then subtract α and divide by two. Next we take the tangent of both sides and then apply the tangent sum and difference formulas. Then we substitute 1 for $\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)$ and convert the tangents to mytangents. In this form we can apply Proposition 4.5. Then we simplify the improper fractions and cross multiply. Next we factor out $(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)$ and drop it since point P is on sphere S.

Sum of the 3D Angles.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha + |\beta| + |\gamma| &= \frac{\pi}{2}. \\ \frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2} &= \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad \text{subtract } \alpha \text{ and divide by 2.} \\ \tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) &= \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \quad \text{tangent of both sides.} \\ \frac{\tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right) + \tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)}{1 - \tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)} &= \frac{1 - \tan\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{1 + \tan\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)} \quad \text{expand the tangents.} \\ \frac{\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right) + \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)}{1 - \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)} &= \frac{1 - \text{myt}\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{1 + \text{myt}\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)} \quad \text{Definition 4.1.} \\ \frac{\left(\frac{|y|}{1+x+|z|}\right) + \left(\frac{|z|}{1+x+|y|}\right)}{1 - \left(\frac{|y|}{1+x+|z|}\right)\left(\frac{|z|}{1+x+|y|}\right)} &= \frac{1 - \left(\frac{x}{1+|y|+|z|}\right)}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{1+|y|+|z|}\right)} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.10 and Proposition 4.5.

$$x^2 + |y|^2 + |z|^2 = 1 \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$1 = 1 \quad \text{point P is on S.}$$

□

Theorem 4.6 is a powerful tool that enables us to determine the values of the 3D functions given only β and γ . It is like having to know only one non-orthogonal angle in a right triangle to calculate the 2D functions.

4.2.3. Point P and the 3D Angles.

Each of the 3D angles also share special connection with one of the coordinates of point P. Most of them are interdependent. However, since there are many locations for P that result in the magnitudes of β or γ equaling $\pi/2$, the angle is dependent on the coordinate in those cases. Table 4.2.3 shows this connection. Since by Definition 3.11, $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$ are the coordinates of point P, the significance of this cannot be understated. As in 2D trigonometry, when the 3D functions increase or decrease, their related angles also tend to increase or decrease.

TABLE 2. Point P and the 3D Angles

Condition	iff	iff	iff	if	iff	if	if	iff	if
Coordinate	x=-1	x=0	x=1	y=-1	y=0	y=1	z=-1	z=0	z=1
3D Angle	$\alpha=-\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\alpha=0$	$\alpha=\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\beta=-\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\beta=0$	$\beta=\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\gamma=-\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\gamma=0$	$\gamma=\frac{\pi}{2}$

The derivation of the 3D angles, their relationship with $\pi/2$ and connection with the coordinates of point P are significantly similar to the properties of the 2D angles.

5. FUNCTION DERIVATIONS

Given the angles we show how to derive the functions. So that we do not have to prove all the different cases that occur due to absolute values in the initial equations, we replace the absolute values with sign variables. They enables us to determine all the cases at once. When we need to switch the sign variables back to absolute values, they are not multiplied by their associated variable. Instead, they are multiplied by mytangent of half the angle associated with the variable. To handle this we have a lemma.

Lemma 5.1 (Sign Variable to myt($|\delta|/2$)). *If d and δ have the same sign, then*

$$\text{myt}(\delta/2)\hat{d} = \text{myt}(|\delta|/2).$$

Sign Variable to myt($|\delta|/2$). Since myt is restricted to $[-\pi, \pi]$ and we are dividing δ by 2, the sign of the output of myt is the sign its input. This allows us to move the sign variable inside the myt. Knowing that d and δ have the same sign, we can convert the sign variable to absolute value of δ . \square

5.1. 2D Function Derivations.

We derive $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ given the angles α_{2D} and β_{2D} on the unit circle.

5.1.1. $\cos 2D$ Derivation.

Proposition 5.2 ($\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ Derivation). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^2 and point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S , then*

$$\cos 2D(\beta_{2D}) = \frac{-\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}$$

In the proof we start with the 2D Half Angle Tangents proposition and apply the Sum of the 2D Angles theorem to replace α_{2D} . After that we simplify and remove the absolute values with sign variables. Then we solve for y in this equation and in the second equation from the 2D Half Angle Tangents proposition. Next we substitute one y into the other equation, and solve for x . Then we convert the sign variables back to absolute values and simplify. To finish we replace x with $\cos 2D$. Note that by definition β_{2D} is on the unit circle S and is limited to the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$.

$\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ Derivation.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{myt}(\alpha_{2D}/2) &= \frac{x}{1+|y|} && \text{Proposition 4.2.} \\ \text{myt}\left(\frac{\pi/2 - |\beta_{2D}|}{2}\right) &= \frac{x}{1+|y|} && \text{Theorem 4.3.} \\ \frac{1 - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)}{1 + \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)} &= \frac{x}{1+|y|} && \text{tangent difference formula.} \\ \frac{1 - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)}{1 + \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)} &= \frac{x}{1+y\hat{y}} && \text{Lemma 3.2.} \\ y &= \frac{-\text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)x - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - x + 1}{\hat{y}(\text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - 1)} && \text{solve for y.} \\ \text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2) &= \frac{y}{1+x} && \text{Proposition 4.2.} \\ y &= \text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)(1+x) && \text{solve for y.} \\ \text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)(1+x) &= \frac{-\text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2)x - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - x + 1}{\hat{y}(\text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - 1)} && \text{substitute y.} \\ x &= \frac{-\text{myt}\left(\frac{\beta_{2D}}{2}\right)\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta_{2D}|}{2}\right)\hat{y} + \text{myt}\left(\frac{\beta_{2D}}{2}\right)\hat{y} - \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta_{2D}|}{2}\right) + 1}{\text{myt}\left(\frac{\beta_{2D}}{2}\right)\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta_{2D}|}{2}\right)\hat{y} - \text{myt}\left(\frac{\beta_{2D}}{2}\right)\hat{y} + \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta_{2D}|}{2}\right) + 1} \\ &&& \text{solve for x.} \\ x &= \frac{-\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) - \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + \text{myt}(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1} \\ &&& \text{Lemma 5.1.} \\ x &= \frac{-\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1} && \text{simplify.} \\ \cos 2D(\beta_{2D}) &= \frac{-\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1} && \text{Definition 3.5.} \end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 5.2 enables us to calculate $\cos 2D$ given only one angle, β_{2D} .

5.1.2. $\sin 2D_1$ Derivation.

To derive $\sin 2D_1$, we continue the process in the proof for $\cos 2D$.

Proposition 5.3 ($\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ Derivation). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 and point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S , then*

$$\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \frac{2\text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}$$

In the proof, we take the equation for x above and substitute it into the equation for y . Then we simplify and replace y with $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$.

$\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ Derivation.

$$y = \text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)(1 + x) \quad \text{from above.}$$

$$y = \text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)\left(1 + \frac{-\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1}\right) \quad \text{substitute x from above.}$$

$$y = \frac{2\text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1} \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) = \frac{2\text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)}{\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1} \quad \text{definition 3.5.}$$

□

Now we can also calculate $\sin 2D_1$ given only β_{2D} . Notice that by using the tangent half angle formula, $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ evaluate to the traditional \cos and \sin as expected. Also note that the denominator for the 2D functions is the same and always positive. We see this again for the 3D functions.

5.2. 3D Function Derivations.

Deriving the 3D functions, $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$ given angles α , β , and γ on the unit sphere takes several steps. The derivation is based on the 3D Half Angle Tangents equations and follows the pattern established in the derivation of the 2D functions. Note that the angles are defined by points on the unit sphere, so the domains of the functions are restricted to $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$. Since the other 3D functions can be derived directly from $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$, we forgo investigating the remaining functions.

In the proofs of derivation of the 2D functions, some of the equations barely fit on the page. Unfortunately, for the 3D derivations even the results are too large to fit. To overcome this we introduce two new variables to substitute for $\text{myt}(|\beta|/2)$ and $\text{myt}(|\gamma|/2)$.

Definition 5.4 (myt Variables).

$$b = \text{myt}(|\beta|/2)$$

$$g = \text{myt}(|\gamma|/2)$$

5.2.1. $\cos 3D$ Derivation.

Proposition 5.5 ($\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ Derivation). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 and point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , then*

$$\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) = \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}.$$

To prove this we start with the first equation in Proposition 4.5. Then we replace α using Theorem 4.6 and apply the tangent difference and sum formulas. Next we replace the absolute values around the y 's and z 's with sign variables and solve for z . Then we take the other two equations in Proposition 4.5, switch the absolute values to sign variables and solve for z in them. Next we substitute for z giving us two equations with x and y then solve for y . We substitute one into the other and solve for x . Next we replace the sign variables with absolute values. Finally replace x using Definition 3.11.

$\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ Derivation.

$$\text{myt}(\alpha/2) = \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|} \quad \text{Proposition 4.5.}$$

$$\text{myt}\left(\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - (|\beta| + |\gamma|)}{2}\right) = \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|} \quad \text{Theorem 4.6.}$$

$$\frac{\text{myt}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) - \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)}{\text{myt}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + 1} = \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|} \quad \text{tangent difference formula.}$$

$$(1 - \text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right))(1 + |y| + |z|) = (\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2} + \frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + 1)x \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{b+g}{1-bg}\right)(1 + |y| + |z|) = \left(\frac{b+g}{1-bg} + 1\right)x \quad \text{tangent sum formula.}$$

$$(1 - bg - b - g)(1 + |y| + |z|) = (b + g + 1 - bg)x \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$(1 - bg - b - g)(1 + y\hat{y} + z\hat{z}) = (b + g + 1 - bg)x \quad \text{Lemma 3.2.}$$

$$z = \frac{bgx - bgy\hat{y} - bg - bx - by\hat{y} - b - gx - gy\hat{y} - g - x + y\hat{y} + 1}{\hat{z}(bg + b + g - 1)} \quad \text{solve for z.}$$

$$\text{myt}(\beta/2) = \frac{y}{1 + x + |z|}, \quad \text{myt}(\gamma/2) = \frac{z}{1 + x + |y|} \quad \text{Proposition 4.5.}$$

$$\text{myt}(\beta/2) = \frac{y}{1 + x + z\hat{z}}, \quad \text{myt}(\gamma/2) = \frac{z}{1 + x + y\hat{y}} \quad \text{Lemma 3.2.}$$

$$z = \frac{-\text{myt}(\beta/2)x - \text{myt}(\beta/2) + y}{\text{myt}(\beta/2)z\hat{z}}, \quad z = \text{myt}(\gamma/2)(1 + x + y\hat{y}) \quad \text{solve for z.}$$

$$y = \frac{2 \text{myt}(\beta/2)x(bg - 1)}{\text{myt}(\beta/2)bg\hat{y} + \text{myt}(\beta/2)b\hat{y} + \text{myt}(\beta/2)g\hat{y} - \text{myt}(\beta/2)\hat{y} + bg + b + g - 1}$$

substitute z, solve for y.

$$y = \frac{2 \text{myt}(\beta/2)x(bg - 1)}{b^2g + b^2 + bg - b + bg + b + g - 1} \quad \text{Lemma 5.1.}$$

$$y = \frac{2 \text{myt}(\beta/2)x(bg - 1)}{b^2g + b^2 + 2bg + g - 1} \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$y = \frac{b(gx - g - x - 1) - \text{myt}(\gamma/2)\hat{z}(b(gx + g + x + 1) + gx + g - x - 1) - gx - g - x + 1}{\hat{y}(\text{myt}(\gamma/2)\hat{z} + 1)(bg + b + g - 1)}$$

substitute z, solve for y.

$$y = \frac{b(gx - g - x - 1) - g(b(gx + g + x + 1) + gx + g - x - 1) - gx - g - x + 1}{\hat{y}(g + 1)(bg + b + g - 1)}$$

simplify.

$$x = \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{\text{myt}(\beta/2)\hat{y}(2bg^2 + 2bg - 2g - 2) + b^2g^2 + b^2 + 2bg^2 + 2b + g^2 + 1}$$

substitute y, solve for x.

$$x = \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{b(2bg^2 + 2bg - 2g - 2) + b^2g^2 + b^2 + 2bg^2 + 2b + g^2 + 1} \quad \text{Lemma 5.1.}$$

$$x = \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1} \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) = \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1} \quad \text{Definition 3.11.}$$

□

Proposition 5.5 allows us to determine $\cos 3D$ given only β and γ . Figure 4 shows graphs of $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$. The first uses $(\beta, \gamma, \cos 3D)$ Cartesian coordinates. The second is in polar coordinates. Note that the polar graph is a sphere of radius 0.5 centered at $(0.5, 0, 0)$.

FIGURE 4. $\cos 3D$

5.2.2. $\sin 3D_1$ Derivation.

We continue the thought process from the $\cos 3D$ derivation for $\sin 3D_1$.

Proposition 5.6 ($\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ Derivation). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 and point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , then*

$$\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = 2\text{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-bg^2 - bg + g + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}.$$

In the proof we start with one of the equations from Proposition 5.5 that was solved for y . Next we substitute x and simplify. We finish by substituting $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ for y .

$\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ *Derivation.*

$$y = \frac{2 \operatorname{myt}(\beta/2)x(bg - 1)}{b^2g + b^2 + 2bg + g - 1} \quad \text{from Proposition 5.5.}$$

$$y = 2 \operatorname{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-bg^2 - bg + g + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}$$

substitute x , simplify.

$$\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = 2 \operatorname{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-bg^2 - bg + g + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}$$

Definition 3.11.

□

Now we can also calculate $\sin 3D_1$ given only the two solid angles β and γ . Figure 5 shows the similarity with the traditional 2D sine function. The polar graph is a sphere with radius 0.5 centered at $(0, 0.5, 0)$.

FIGURE 5. $\sin 3D_1$

5.2.3. $\sin 3D_2$ *Derivation.*

We use the information from the derivations of $\cos 3D$ and $\sin 3D_1$ for $\sin 3D_2$.

Proposition 5.7 ($\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ Derivation). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 and point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , then*

$$\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = 2 \operatorname{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-b^2g - bg + b + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}.$$

We begin with one of the equations in Proposition 5.5 that was solved for z and substitute both x and y . Next we convert the sign variables to absolute values and simplify. Finally we substitute $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ for z .

$\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ Derivation.

$$z = \text{myt}(\gamma/2)(1 + x + y\hat{y}) \quad \text{from Proposition 5.5.}$$

$$z = 2 \text{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-b^2g - bg + b + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}$$

substitute x and y, Lemma 5.1.

$$\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = 2 \text{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-b^2g - bg + b + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}$$

Definition 3.11.

□

Proposal 5.7 allows us to calculate $\sin 3D_2$, hence determining the final coordinate for Point P given β and γ . The first graph in Figure 6 is identical to the Cartesian graph for $\sin 3D_1$ rotated $\pi/2$ radians. As expected, the polar graph is a sphere with radius 0.5 centered at $(0, 0, 0.5)$.

FIGURE 6. $\sin 3D_2$

The derivations of the functions allow us to examine their properties. First we must define the functions when the magnitudes of the angles are too large for the unit circle or unit sphere.

6. FUNCTION VALUES FOR ANGLES OFF S

We have derived the functions for 2D angles on the unit circle and for 3D angles on the unit sphere. Now we define the functions when $|\beta_{2D}| > \pi$ and $|\beta| + |\gamma| > \pi$ based on those values.

6.1. 2D Function Values for \Re Domain.

If $|\beta_{2D}| > \pi$, $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are determined by converting β_{2D} to the form $\beta_0 + i\pi$ where $i \bmod 2 = 0$ such that $|\beta_0| \leq \pi$, then calculating the values given by β_0 . In effect, this translates the functions by 2π increments. Although, the definition below is a complicated way to say this, it can be easily extended to 3D.

Definition 6.1 (2D Function Values for \mathfrak{R}). Let

$$\beta_{2D} = \beta_0 + i\pi \text{ such that } i \bmod 2 = 0 \text{ and } |\beta_0| \leq \pi,$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 2D(\beta_{2D}) &= \cos 2D(\beta_0). \\ \sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D}) &= \sin 2D_1(\beta_0). \end{aligned}$$

6.2. 3D Function Values for \mathfrak{R}^2 Domain.

So far we can calculate 3D trigonometric functions when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$. This restriction allows for P to be each point on sphere S. For the circular 2D functions, when $|\beta_{2D}| > \pi$, the functions are determined by translating the values in the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$. We extend this concept for the spherical functions. When $|\beta| + |\gamma| > \pi$, the values are obtained by translating the square with area $2\pi^2$ that is defined when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$.

When $|\beta| + |\gamma| > \pi$, $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are determined by converting (β, γ) to the form $(\beta_0 + i\pi, \gamma_0 + j\pi)$ where $(i + j) \bmod 2 = 0$ such that $|\beta_0| + |\gamma_0| \leq \pi$, then calculating the values given by β_0 and γ_0 . Figure 7 shows the periodic intervals with their (i, j) indexes.

Definition 6.2 (3D Function Values for \mathfrak{R}^2). Let

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= \beta_0 + i\pi \text{ and } \gamma = \gamma_0 + j\pi \text{ such that} \\ i \text{ and } j &\in \mathbb{Z}, (i + j) \bmod 2 = 0, \text{ and } |\beta_0| + |\gamma_0| \leq \pi, \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= \cos 3D(\beta_0, \gamma_0) \\ \sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= \sin 3D_1(\beta_0, \gamma_0) \\ \sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= \sin 3D_2(\beta_0, \gamma_0) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 6.2 overcomes the restriction that β and γ must be angles on sphere S. It allows them to be each real number. Now we can investigate the properties of the functions.

7. FUNCTION PROPERTIES

First we discuss the properties of the 2D functions. Then we apply similar methods to prove the properties for the 3D functions.

7.1. 2D Function Properties.

Since $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are equivalent to the traditional trigonometric functions, we know that they are periodic, symmetric, and continuous. However, we are going to prove these properties using the tools we have built in this paper. The functions $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ both have a period of 2π . The function $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ has even symmetry. The function $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ has odd symmetry. The functions $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are both continuous for $\beta_{2D} \in \mathfrak{R}$.

7.1.1. 2D Functions are Periodic.

FIGURE 7. 3D Function Periodic Intervals

Since by definition to determine values in \Re , the 2D functions are translated by 2π when $|\beta_{2D}| > \pi$, they are periodic.

Theorem 7.1 (2D Functions are Periodic). $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are periodic with a period of 2π that is repeated every $i\pi$ where $i \bmod 2 = 0$.

2D Functions are Periodic. Definition 6.1, 2D Function Values for \Re Domain, explains that the functions for the initial interval surrounding the origin, $|\beta_{2D}| \leq \pi$, is translated to determine values for $|\beta_{2D}| > \pi$ and sets the period to 2π . \square

7.1.2. *2D Functions are Symmetric.*

$\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are symmetric.

Theorem 7.2 ($\cos 2D$ Symmetry). $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ has even symmetry.

$\cos 2D$ Symmetry. Since the absolute value of β_{2D} is always used in Proposition 5.2, $\cos 2D$ is even. \square

Theorem 7.3 ($\sin 2D_1$ Symmetry). $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ has odd symmetry.

$\sin 2D_1$ *Symmetry*. In the equation for calculating $\sin 2D_1$, Proposition 5.3, the absolute value of β_{2D} is taken in the the denominator but not in the numerator. Since mytangent is only defined in $[-\pi, \pi]$, the sign of β_{2D} is the same as $\text{myt}(\beta_{2D}/2)$. This causes $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ to be odd. \square

7.1.3. 2D Functions are Continuous.

To prove that the $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are continuous, we first show that they are continuous at the borders of the periodic intervals and then show that they are continuous inside the intervals.

We know that the periodic borders for the initial interval of the 2D functions are at $\pm\pi$. To prove the functions are continuous at the borders of adjacent periodic intervals, we need a lemma about the location of P at the borders.

Lemma 7.4 (Point P when $|\beta_{2D}| = \pi$). *Let S be the unit circle centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^2 , point P with coordinates (x, y) be on S, and $|\beta_{2D}| = \pi$, then*

point P has coordinates $(-1, 0)$.

Point P when $|\beta_{2D}| = \pi$.

$$\begin{aligned} |\beta_{2D}| &= \pi. \\ \pi/2 - \alpha_{2D} &= \pi \quad \text{Theorem 4.3.} \\ \alpha_{2D} &= -\pi/2 \quad \text{simplify.} \\ \text{myt}((-\pi/2)/2) &= \frac{x}{1+|y|} \quad \text{Proposition 4.2.} \\ -1 &= \frac{x}{1+|y|} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ P &= (-1, 0) \quad \text{P is on circle S.} \end{aligned}$$

\square

Lemma 7.5 (2D Functions are Continuous at the Borders). *The functions $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are continuous at the borders of adjacent periodic intervals.*

2D Functions are Continuous at the Borders. By Definition 3.5 and Lemma 7.4, $\cos 2D$ is -1 and $\sin 2D_1$ is 0 at the borders of the periodic intervals. Since the functions are constants at the borders they are continuous for adjacent periodic intervals. \square

Now we need a lemma to show that $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are continuous inside the periodic intervals.

Lemma 7.6 (2D Functions are Continuous inside the Periodic Intervals). *The functions $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are continuous inside the periodic intervals.*

2D Functions are Continuous inside the Periodic Intervals. We know from Propositions 5.2 and 5.3 that $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are composed of the addition, subtraction, and multiplication of the continuous function mytangent. We only have to show that there is no division by zero for them to be continuous. Since the denominator for both the functions, $\text{myt}^2(|\beta_{2D}|/2) + 1$, is always positive, $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are continuous inside the periodic intervals. \square

Theorem 7.7 (2D Functions are Continuous in \mathfrak{R}).

The functions $\cos 2D(\beta_{2D})$ and $\sin 2D_1(\beta_{2D})$ are continuous in \mathfrak{R} .

2D Functions are Continuous in \mathfrak{R} . Since by Lemma 7.5 $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are continuous at the borders of the periodic intervals and by Lemma 7.6 they are continuous inside the periodic intervals, $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are continuous in \mathfrak{R} . \square

We have shown that $\cos 2D$ and $\sin 2D_1$ are periodic, symmetric, and continuous. Now we examine these properties for the 3D functions using similar methods.

7.2. 3D Function Properties.

We are ready to show that the properties of the 2D functions is extended to $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$. First we prove that they are periodic. Next we show their symmetry. Then we examine their continuity.

7.2.1. 3D Functions are Periodic.

Showing that $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are periodic is simple due to the way they are defined for \mathfrak{R}^2

Theorem 7.8 (3D Functions are Periodic). *The functions $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are periodic with a period of $2\pi^2$ that is repeated for $(i\pi, j\pi)$ where i and j are integers and $(i + j) \bmod 2 = 0$.*

3D Functions are Periodic. The proof that the 3D functions are periodic comes directly from Definition 6.2, 3D Function Values for \mathfrak{R}^2 . It explains that the functions for the initial interval surrounding the origin when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$ is translated to determine values for $|\beta| + |\gamma| > \pi$ and sets the period to $2\pi^2$ for $(i\pi, j\pi)$ where $(i + j) \bmod 2 = 0$. \square

7.2.2. 3D Functions are Symmetric.

The symmetry of the 3D functions is similar to the 2D functions. The function $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ has even symmetry wrt both β and γ . The function $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$'s symmetry is odd wrt β and even wrt γ . The function $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ has even symmetry for β and odd symmetry for γ . Their symmetry is determined by the which variables are inside absolute values in the equations to calculate them given β and γ .

$\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ Symmetry.

Theorem 7.9 ($\cos 3D$ Symmetry). *The function $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$ has even symmetry wrt both β and γ .*

Proof. Since β and γ are always encapsulated by absolute values in the $\cos 3D$ Derivation Proposition 5.5, $\cos 3D$ is even wrt β and γ . \square

$\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ Symmetry.

Theorem 7.10 ($\sin 3D_1$ Symmetry). *The function $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ has odd symmetry wrt β and even symmetry wrt γ .*

Proof. In the $\sin 3D_1$ Derivation Proposition 5.6, the absolute values of β and γ are always used in the denominator. In the numerator mytangent of $\beta/2$ the only variable that is not inside absolute values is multiplied by the rest of the terms, so $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is odd wrt β and even wrt γ . \square

$\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ Symmetry.

Theorem 7.11 ($\sin 3D_2$ Symmetry). *The function $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ has even symmetry wrt β and odd symmetry wrt γ .*

Proof. Since γ is the only variable that is not embedded in absolute values and $\text{myt}(\gamma/2)$ is multiplied by the rest of the terms in Proposition 5.7, $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is even wrt β and odd wrt γ . \square

7.2.3. 3D Functions are Continuous.

To show that $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are continuous, we first prove that the functions are continuous at the borders of the periodic intervals when $\gamma = \pm\beta \pm i\pi$ where $i \bmod 2 = 1$, then prove they are continuous inside the initial interval surrounding the origin.

Continuity at the Borders.

To prove the continuity from one periodic interval to an adjacent interval we need a lemma based on Theorem 4.6.

Lemma 7.12 (Point P when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi$). *Let S be the unit sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^3 , point P with coordinates (x, y, z) be on S , and $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi$, then*

point P has coordinates $(-1, 0, 0)$.

Point P when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi$.

$$|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi.$$

$$\pi/2 - \alpha = \pi \quad \text{Theorem 4.6.}$$

$$\alpha = -\pi/2 \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$\text{myt}((-\pi/2)/2) = \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|} \quad \text{Proposition 4.5.}$$

$$-1 = \frac{x}{1 + |y| + |z|} \quad \text{simplify.}$$

$$P = (-1, 0, 0) \quad P \text{ is on sphere } S.$$

\square

Now we can show continuity from one periodic interval to another.

Lemma 7.13 (3D Functions are Continuous at the Borders). *The functions $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are continuous between two adjacent periodic intervals.*

3D Functions are Continuous at the Borders. We know from Lemma 7.12 that point P is $(-1, 0, 0)$ at the borders of the periodic intervals. From Definition 3.11 we conclude that at the borders $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) = -1$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = 0$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = 0$. Since the functions are constant at the borders of the periodic intervals, they are continuous from one interval to the next. \square

Continuity when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$.

We know that $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are composed of the sum, difference, and product of the continuous function myt when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$. To prove that they are continuous on the initial periodic interval surrounding the origin we must only show that there is no division by 0. First, we show that the common denominator for the functions is always positive for $|\beta| + |\gamma| < \pi$. Then we prove that the denominator is positive at the border when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi$.

Note that in the propositions for the derivation of $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ the denominators are all the same. We are going to define this as function $\text{den}(\beta, \gamma)$.

Definition 7.14 (Common Denominator).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{den}(\beta, \gamma) &= 3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1. \\ &= 3\text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + 2\text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + \text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right) \\ &\quad + 2\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) - 2\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\text{myt}\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + \text{myt}^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 7.15 (Denominator Interior is Positive). *den*(β, γ) is positive when $|\gamma| + |\beta| < \pi$.

First we determine the first order partial derivatives for $\text{den}(\beta, \gamma)$. Then we set them to 0 and solve for β and γ to get our critical points. Unfortunately the determinate for the Hessian matrix evaluates to 0, so we compare the critical point to a nearby test point to determine if it is a minimum or maximum. Since the function $\text{myt}(\theta)$ equals \tan when $|\theta| < \pi/2$ and $|\theta|$ cannot be $\pi/2$ if $|\beta| + |\gamma| < \pi$, we use tangent to determine the partials.

Denominator Interior is Positive.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{den}_\beta &= 3\sec^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + 2\sec^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) \\ &\quad + \sec^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right) + \sec^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) - \sec^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right). \\ \text{den}_\gamma &= 3\tan^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\sec^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) + \tan^2\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\sec^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) \\ &\quad + 2\tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\sec^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) - \tan\left(\frac{|\beta|}{2}\right)\sec^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right) \\ &\quad + \sec^2\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right)\tan\left(\frac{|\gamma|}{2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

If we set den_β and den_γ to zero and solve for β and γ , the results are one critical point at $(0, 0)$. Evaluating the denominator at the critical point gives us $\text{den}(0, 0) = 1$. There is only one critical point, so it does not matter where the test point is as long as it is not $(0, 0)$ and $|\beta| + |\gamma| < \pi$. Since $\text{den}(0.1, 0.2) \approx 1.004115$, we conclude that $(0, 0)$ is a minimum and the denominator is always positive for $|\beta| + |\gamma| < \pi$. \square

Lemma 7.16 (Denominator Border is Positive). *den*(β, γ) is positive when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi$.

Denominator Border is Positive. First we replace all the $|\gamma|$ in den with $\pi - |\beta|$. The partial derivative for this is 0 at four critical points, $(\pm\pi/2, \pm\pi/2)$ where den evaluates to 8. At another test point on the border $\text{den}(\pi/3, 2\pi/3) \approx 9.952135$, so the critical points are minimums and the denominator is always positive at the borders of the periodic intervals. \square

Lemma 7.17 (3D Functions are Continuous in the Periodic Intervals). *The functions $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are continuous when $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$.*

Proof. By Lemmas 7.15 and 7.16 $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are composed of the addition, subtraction, multiplication, and non-zero division of continuous functions within the periodic interval defined by $|\beta| + |\gamma| \leq \pi$, so they are continuous in this region. \square

Theorem 7.18 (3D Functions are Continuous). *The functions $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are continuous on \mathbb{R}^2 .*

3D Functions are Continuous. Since $\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ are continuous from one periodic interval to an adjacent interval by Lemma 7.13 and are continuous inside the periodic intervals by Lemma 7.17, they are continuous on \mathbb{R}^2 . \square

These theorems show that the properties of the 2D functions are extended to the 3D functions. Since they are also periodic, symmetric, and continuous $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$ could be powerful tools for mathematical analysis.

8. N-DIMENSIONAL TRIGONOMETRY

The concepts that we discussed for 2D and 3D can be extended to higher N-spaces. First we define the ND angles and functions. Then we list some conjectures about the their properties.

8.1. ND Angles.

The ND angles follow the same pattern established for the 2D and 3D trigonometric angles.

Definition 8.1 (ND Angle Definitions).

Let

Ω_n equal the measure of a orthogonal angle for that N-space.

S be the unit N-sphere centered at the origin in \mathfrak{R}^n .

P be a point on S with coordinates $(x, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-1})$.

$$\vec{p} = \overrightarrow{(x, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-1})}.$$

$$\vec{v}_0 = \overrightarrow{(1, 0, 0, \dots, 0)}.$$

$$\vec{v}_1 = \overrightarrow{(0, \hat{y}_1, 0, \dots, 0)}.$$

$$\vec{v}_i = \overrightarrow{(0, 0, \dots, \hat{y}_i, 0, \dots, 0)}.$$

$$\vec{v}_{n-1} = \overrightarrow{(0, 0, \dots, \hat{y}_{n-1})}.$$

then

α is the angle defined by vectors $\vec{p}, \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_{n-1}$ and has the same sign as x.

β_i is the angle defined by vectors $\vec{v}_0, \vec{v}_1, \dots, \vec{v}_{i-1}, \vec{p}, \vec{v}_{i+1}, \dots, \vec{v}_{n-1}$

and has the same sign as y_i .

8.2. ND Functions.

The ND functions also conform to the discussed paradigm.

Definition 8.2 (ND Function Definitions).

$$\cos ND(\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{n-1}) = x.$$

$$\sin ND_i(\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{n-1}) = y_i.$$

8.3. Properties of ND Angles and Functions.

Here is a list of our conjectures for ND trigonometry.

- (1) $\alpha \in [-\Omega_n, \Omega_n]$.
- (2) $\beta_i \in [-2\Omega_n, 2\Omega_n]$.
- (3) $\alpha + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} |\beta_i| = \Omega_n$.
- (4) Iff $x = 0$, then $\alpha = 0$. Iff $x = \pm 1$, then $\alpha = \pm\Omega_n$. Iff $y_i = 0$, then $\beta_i = 0$.
Iff $y_i = \pm 1$, then $\beta_i = \pm\Omega_n$.
- (5) $\cos ND^2(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sin ND_i^2(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1}) = 1$.
- (6) $\cos ND$ and $\sin ND_i$ are periodic.
- (7) $\cos ND(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1})$ is even with respect to all β_i . $\sin ND_i(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1})$ is odd with respect to β_i and even with respect to the other β_{is} .

- (8) $\cos\text{ND}$ and $\sin\text{ND}_i$ are continuous on \mathfrak{R}^{n-1} .
- (9) When the domain of the functions is restricted to $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} |\beta_i| < 2\Omega_n$, the points $(\cos\text{ND}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1}), \sin\text{ND}_1(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1}), \dots, \sin\text{ND}_{n-1}(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1}))$ have a one-to-one relation to the points on the unit N-sphere S except for point $(-1, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$ that occurs multiple times since it corresponds to the functions when $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} |\beta_i| = 2\Omega_n$.
- (10) If L is the line through the origin and point P, then the tangentND_i , cotangentND_i , sangentND_j , and cosangentND_j functions are defined by the coordinates of the intersections of L and the $x = 1, y_1 = 1, \dots, y_{n-1} = 1$ (n-1)-spaces.
If M is the (n-1)-space that is orthogonal to L containing P, then the secantND and cosecantND_i functions are defined by the coordinates of the intersections of M and the axes.

Some of these conjectures such as (4) and (5) can be proved directly from the definitions of the ND angles and functions. Others are not so simple to prove and should be investigated.

APPENDIX A. 3D FUNCTION DEGENERATE FORMS

When α , β , or γ is zero, $\cos 3\text{D}(\beta, \gamma)$, $\sin 3\text{D}_1(\beta, \gamma)$, and $\sin 3\text{D}_2(\beta, \gamma)$ can be expressed in terms of the conventional 2D sine and cosine functions. The reason for this is that the magnitudes of the orthogonal angles for 2D and 3D are equal.

A.1. Degenerates when $\beta = 0$.

When $\beta = 0$, the degenerate form of $\cos 3\text{D}(0, \gamma)$ is $\cos(\gamma)$ and the degenerate form of $\sin 3\text{D}_2(0, \gamma)$ is $\sin(\gamma)$.

corollary A.1 (Degenerate $\cos 3\text{D}$, $\beta = 0$). *If $\beta = 0$, $\cos 3\text{D}(0, \gamma) = \cos(\gamma)$.*

Degenerate $\cos 3\text{D}$, $\beta = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 3\text{D}(\beta, \gamma) &= \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1} \\ \cos 3\text{D}(0, \gamma) &= \frac{-(0)^2g^2 - 2(0)^2g - (0)^2 - 2(0)g^2 - 2(0)g - g^2 + 1}{3(0)^2g^2 + 2(0)^2g + (0)^2 + 2(0)g^2 - 2(0)g + g^2 + 1} \quad \text{myt}(|\beta|/2) = 0. \\ &= \frac{-g^2 + 1}{g^2 + 1} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ &= \cos(\gamma) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.} \end{aligned}$$

□

corollary A.2 (Degenerate $\sin 3\text{D}_2$, $\beta = 0$). *If $\beta = 0$, $\sin 3\text{D}_2(0, \gamma) = \sin(\gamma)$.*

Degenerate $\sin 3D_2$, $\beta = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= 2\text{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-b^2g - bg + b + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}. \\ \sin 3D_2(0, \gamma) &= 2\text{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-(0)^2g - (0)g + (0) + 1}{3(0)^2g^2 + 2(0)^2g + (0)^2 + 2(0)g^2 - 2(0)g + g^2 + 1} \\ &= \text{myt}(|\beta|/2) = 0. \\ &= \frac{2\text{myt}(\gamma/2)}{b^2 + 1} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ &= \sin(\gamma) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.}\end{aligned}$$

□

A.2. Degenerates when $\gamma = 0$.

When $\gamma = 0$, the degenerate form of $\cos 3D(\beta, 0)$ is $\cos(\beta)$ and the degenerate form of $\sin 3D_1(\beta, 0)$ is $\sin(\beta)$.

corollary A.3 (Degenerate $\cos 3D$, $\gamma = 0$). *If $\gamma = 0$, $\cos 3D(\beta, 0) = \cos(\beta)$.*

Degenerate $\cos 3D$, $\gamma = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\cos 3D(\beta, \gamma) &= \frac{-b^2g^2 - 2b^2g - b^2 - 2bg^2 - 2bg - g^2 + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}. \\ \cos 3D(\beta, 0) &= \frac{-b^2(0)^2 - 2b^2(0) - b^2 - 2b(0)^2 - 2b(0) - (0)^2 + 1}{3b^2(0)^2 + 2b^2(0) + b^2 + 2b(0)^2 - 2b(0) + (0)^2 + 1}. \quad \text{myt}(|\gamma|/2) = 0. \\ &= \frac{-b^2 + 1}{b^2 + 1} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ &= \cos(\beta) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.}\end{aligned}$$

□

corollary A.4 (Degenerate $\sin 3D_1$, $\gamma = 0$). *If $\gamma = 0$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, 0) = \sin(\beta)$.*

Degenerate $\sin 3D_1$, $\gamma = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= 2\text{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-bg^2 - bg + g + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}. \\ \sin 3D_1(\beta, 0) &= 2\text{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-b(0)^2 - b(0) + (0) + 1}{3b^2(0)^2 + 2b^2(0) + b^2 + 2b(0)^2 - 2b(0) + (0)^2 + 1} \\ &= \text{myt}(|\gamma|/2) = 0. \\ &= \frac{2\text{myt}(\beta/2)}{b^2 + 1} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ &= \sin(\beta) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.}\end{aligned}$$

□

A.3. Degenerates when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$ ($\alpha = 0$).

When $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$, the degenerate form of $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma)$ is $\sin(\beta)$ and the degenerate form of $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma)$ is $\sin(\gamma)$. We need a lemma for this case to express b in terms of g and vice versa.

Lemma A.5 (b and g when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$). *If $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$, then*

$$b = \frac{-g + 1}{g + 1}.$$

$$g = \frac{-b + 1}{b + 1}.$$

b and g when $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$.

$$|\theta_1| + |\theta_2| = \pi/2.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tan(|\theta_2|/2) &= \tan(\pi/4 - |\theta_1|/2) \quad \text{subtract } |\theta_1|, \text{ divide by two, and tangent.} \\ &= \frac{\tan(\pi/4) - \tan(|\theta_1|/2)}{1 + \tan(\pi/4)\tan(|\theta_1|/2)} \quad \text{tangent difference formula.} \\ &= \frac{-\tan(|\theta_1|/2) + 1}{\tan(|\theta_1|/2) + 1} \quad \text{simplify.} \\ \text{myt}(|\theta_2|/2) &= \frac{-\text{myt}(|\theta_1|/2) + 1}{\text{myt}(|\theta_1|/2) + 1} \quad \text{Definition 4.1.} \\ b &= \frac{-g + 1}{g + 1} \quad \text{substitute } \gamma \text{ for } \theta_1 \text{ and } \beta \text{ for } \theta_2, \text{ Definition 5.4.} \\ g &= \frac{-b + 1}{b + 1} \quad \text{substitute } \beta \text{ for } \theta_1 \text{ and } \gamma \text{ for } \theta_2, \text{ Definition 5.4.} \end{aligned}$$

□

corollary A.6 (Degenerate $\sin 3D_1$, $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$). *If $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$, $\sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) = \sin(\beta)$.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \sin 3D_1(\beta, \gamma) &= 2\text{myt}(\beta/2) \frac{-bg^2 - bg + g + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}. \\ &= \frac{2\text{myt}(\beta/2)}{b^2 + 1} \quad \text{Lemma A.5, simplify.} \\ &= \sin(\beta) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.} \end{aligned}$$

□

corollary A.7 (Degenerate $\sin 3D_2$, $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$). *If $|\beta| + |\gamma| = \pi/2$, $\sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) = \sin(\gamma)$.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \sin 3D_2(\beta, \gamma) &= 2\text{myt}(\gamma/2) \frac{-b^2g - bg + b + 1}{3b^2g^2 + 2b^2g + b^2 + 2bg^2 - 2bg + g^2 + 1}. \\ &= \frac{2\text{myt}(\gamma/2)}{g^2 + 1} \quad \text{Lemma A.5, simplify.} \\ &= \sin(\gamma) \quad \text{tangent half angle formula.} \end{aligned}$$

□

The degenerate forms of $\cos 3D$, $\sin 3D_1$, and $\sin 3D_2$ are exceptional and only occur since the magnitudes of the orthogonal angles are the same in 2D and 3D. This is not usually the case, so even though the degenerate forms for higher dimensional trigonometric functions may exist when the angles are zero, they probably cannot be directly expressed as a function of the next lower dimension with angles from the current dimension as inputs.

REFERENCES

1. Van Oosterom A, Strackee J (1983), The Solid Angle of a Plane Triangle, IEEE Trans, Biomed, Eng, BME-30 2: 125-126.
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